

Polaron: An AI tool for the characterisation and design of advanced materials

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www.polaron.ai | This manuscript was compiled on September 11, 2024

This paper presents Polaron, an innovative tool that is transforming advanced materials design with generative AI and high-throughput simulation. By leveraging image-based algorithms to analyse microstructural data, the technology rapidly models complex process-structure-performance relationships, significantly accelerating the design process. Initially developed for battery manufacturing, Polaron's approach is now being used across various advanced material applications. This paper outlines the methodologies, technological advancements, and the potential industry impact, underscoring Polaron's role in enhancing material design and manufacturing efficiency.

Advanced Materials Manufacturing | Generative AI | Accelerated Materials Design

Polaron is a tool for the characterisation and design of advanced materials. Advanced materials are any material where the microstructure significantly impacts the performance and so microstructure design is of critical importance. The company was originally a spin-out from the Tools for Learning Research and Design (TLDR) group in the Dyson School of Design Engineering at Imperial College London in 2023. Its platform represents significant improvements on the original intellectual property generated at Imperial in the following key areas:

Materials Characterisation. Polaron has developed a variety of image based materials characterisation tools based on state-of-the-art computer vision models. These allow engineers to rapidly label their data with the assistance of pre-trained models, overcoming some of the inaccuracies of existing methods. This has already been deployed at scale for open-source data projects (1).

Generative AI. The capability to generate 3D volumes from 2D image data was originally developed by Kench and Cooper (2). This method provided an alternative to slow, expensive, and poorly resolved 3D imaging techniques. Although this initial model was impressive, the fidelity of the volumes it generated needed improvement. The version deployed in Polaron is not only much faster and more memory efficient, but also far more accurate, especially for long range feature correlations.

Physics-based performance simulation. The Polaron tool allows for the integration of various physics-based models that allow microstructural insights to be translated into device level performance predictions. One example of these are the GPU accelerated microscale transport models deployed in (3).

Materials optimisation and design. Optimisation workflows can be deployed in the Polaron tool to rapidly find the best performing microstructures and manufacturing parameters for a particular application. This was first demonstrated by Kench *et al.* in a study on Li-ion battery electrodes (4), indicating a step-change in microstructural modelling.

References

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Significance Statement

Polaron is revolutionising the characterisation and design of advanced materials through the innovative application of generative artificial intelligence. The tool leverages state-of-the-art **image-based generative AI** algorithms to analyse microstructural image data, enabling the rapid modelling of complex process-structure-performance relationships. This novel approach not only **accelerates the materials design process** but is also secure-by-design, using enterprise grade security and bespoke model training to ensure data is used securely and specifically. Initially developed for battery electrodes, the methods have broad applicability across various advanced material sectors, offering significant potential to enhance performance, reduce development time, and **support the transition to sustainable technologies**.

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